

Microplastics in aquaculture fish - investigating microplastic exposure in Nile Tilapia

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Microplastics
Translocation
Oreochromis niloticus
Fish organs
Food safety
Py-GC-MS
 μ -FTIR

ABSTRACT

Microplastics (MPs) in fish for consumption are considered a potential pathway for human exposure. While MPs have been widely detected in the digestive tracts of various fish species, their translocation to other organs and edible tissues remains poorly understood. The present study aimed to investigate the potential translocation of MPs in the liver, gonads, and fillet of adult Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) after 7 days of dietary exposure. Adult fish were fed with feed containing a mixture of four polymer types, polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polyamide 6 (PA6), in irregular shapes and sizes ranging from 10 to 350 μ m. The polymers were quantified in the tissues using pyrolysis gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (Py-GC-MS). Minimal MP accumulation was detected in liver and gonad samples, with MPs detected in fewer than 50 % of samples. No MPs were detected in fillet tissue of either control or exposed fish, suggesting no translocation of MPs to edible muscle within the exposure period. Complementary analysis with micro-Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (μ -FTIR) and optical microscopy on fecal matter revealed a high abundance of MPs, suggesting efficient excretion of ingested particles. These results demonstrated that short-term dietary exposure to MPs leads to negligible bioaccumulation in tilapia tissues, highlighting excretion as the dominant elimination pathway. This study provides novel evidence on the limited transfer of MPs for the analyzed size range to edible tissues in aquaculture species, with implications for food safety risk assessment.

1. Introduction

Aquatic food products play a crucial role in meeting the growing global demand, with aquaculture production reaching a record 112.6 million tonnes in 2020, with the mass of farmed animals surpassing wild-caught in 2022 (FAO, 2022). However, the increasing presence of microplastics (MPs) in aquatic environments raises concerns about the safety and quality of farmed fish. MPs can enter aquaculture systems through polluted water sources, fish feed, or abrasion of plastic-based equipment (Zhou et al., 2021). Although aquaculture practices are

becoming more sustainable through the use of recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) (Martins et al., 2010), recent studies indicate that MPs may persist within these systems, leading to potential accumulation and transfer in cultured species (Blonç et al., 2023; Egea-Corbacho et al., 2023; Matias et al., 2023).

The presence of MPs in fish has been widely documented across various species (Gayathri et al., 2024; Ouheddou et al., 2025; Piya-wardhana et al., 2022). Fish primarily ingest MPs when they mistake them for food, accidentally consume them while feeding or drinking, or acquire them through trophic transfer in the food chain (Li et al., 2021).

This article is part of a special issue entitled: Microplastics, Food bioscience, and Health published in Food Bioscience.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2025.108164>

Received 29 June 2025; Received in revised form 28 October 2025; Accepted 22 December 2025

Available online 23 December 2025

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MPs are most frequently detected in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), highlighting their ingestion in fish and making it a key indicator of MP contamination in aquatic ecosystems (Wang et al., 2024). However, evidence suggests that MPs can also be taken up and accumulate in other organs, including the liver (Matias et al., 2023), gills (Pereira et al., 2023; Sun et al., 2025), and muscle tissues (Ferrante et al., 2022; Sefiloglu et al., 2024). The detection of MPs in fillet tissues is of particular concern due to their implications for human exposure. Therefore, it is essential to understand the potential uptake and translocation of the MPs in fish bodies, including the fish fillet.

The accumulation and translocation of MPs in fish are influenced by multiple factors, including environmental MP concentrations, exposure duration, particle size, species, and lifespan (Rojas-Luna et al., 2025). Controlled laboratory experiments using MPs in fish feed or fish tanks are limited, and only a few studies have investigated the translocation in fish organs and tissues (Dawson et al., 2025; Muhib & Rahman, 2024; Piskula et al., 2025; Zeytin et al., 2020). Despite variations in experimental conditions such as MP type, size, exposure duration, and analytical methods, most studies consistently indicate that the GIT is the primary site of accumulation, while uptake in muscle tissues is minimal or undetectable (Dawson et al., 2025; Kim et al., 2020; Muhib & Rahman, 2024). Notably, the majority of these studies use single-polymer fluorescent microspheres for microscopic analysis, whereas research involving a mixture of MPs, relevant to the real environment, remains limited.

The Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) is among the most cultivated freshwater species and constitutes an important source of dietary protein worldwide. Determination of MP uptake and distribution in tilapia is therefore of importance for evaluating potential human exposure through aquaculture products. In this study, adult Nile tilapia reared in a RAS were fed for seven days with a diet containing a mixture of four environmentally relevant polymers with irregular shapes and sizes ranging from 10 to 350 μm . The MPs included polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polyamide-6 (PA6). Following the exposure period, liver, gonad, and fillet of the tilapia were analyzed using pyrolysis gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (Py-GC-MS) to quantify MP concentrations. Fecal matter samples were examined qualitatively using micro-Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (μ -FTIR) and optical microscopy to assess MP excretion. The combined application of Py-GC-MS and μ -FTIR enabled polymer-specific quantification and particle-level visualization, providing complementary capabilities for detecting microplastics in complex biological matrices. Additionally, the efficiency of the applied digestion protocols to each type of tissue and fecal matter was evaluated. By expanding upon the author's previous works (König Kardgar et al., 2024; Sefiloglu et al., 2024), the present study advances the understanding of MP translocation and retention in commercially farmed tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). The findings provide new insights into the biological fate of MPs in aquaculture species and their potential implications for human exposure through seafood consumption.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of MPs and fish feed

The polymer granulates of high-density PE (HDPE) (Polyethylene Lumicene Supertough 22ST05/32ST05, Total Energies), PP (RIGK 1346, Borealis, Austria), PET (Steinbeis PolyVert GmbH, recycled PET (Steinbeis PolyVert GmbH, Plant AT, Völkermarkt, Austria), and PA6 (Sigma Aldrich, USA, CAS no. 25038-54-4) were each mixed and cooled with liquid nitrogen (N_2) for approximately 10 min and subsequently milled using an ultra-centrifugal mill (ZM 200, Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany) equipped with a 1000 μm spacer sieve and a 24-tooth rotor operating at 18,000 U/min. The resulting ground polymer was dried under high vacuum on a Schlenk line for 4 h at 102 mbar, followed by 24 h at 40 °C and 5 mbar. The dried material was then sieved using an air-jet sieving

machine (20 min, 2000 Pa) first with a sieve with pore size of 350 μm , then resulting fraction again with a 10 μm pore size sieve. The particle fraction in the size range of 10–350 μm was used for the experiments.

For the preparation of the spiked fish food, Tilapia Grower food (Skretting, Nutreco N.V., The Netherlands) was utilized, in accordance with the protocol established by (König Kardgar et al., 2024). Briefly, commercial fish food was ground into powder and combined with gelatine, red food colorant, water, and additional particles for the spiked feed. The prepared food was then stored at -20 °C. MPs were incorporated into the feed at a concentration of 2 % (w/w) with equal proportions of PE, PP, PET, and PA6. The control feed was analyzed with μ -FTIR, and no MPs were detected.

2.2. Fish husbandry, feeding, and dissection of fish

The sample collection, feeding experiments, and dissection procedures were previously described in detail by König Kardgar et al. (2024). Briefly, adult male Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*, 600–1000 g; detailed sizes in Table S1) were obtained from Gårdsfisk AB (Åhus, Sweden) and transferred to the Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences, University of Gothenburg. At Gårdsfisk AB, the fish were maintained in PE tanks equipped with PE biofilters. Following transport, the fish were acclimated for 14 days at a density of two individuals per 120 L tank. Water temperature was maintained at 26 ± 1 °C under a 14 h:10 h light: dark cycle, with 33 % of the tank water exchanged daily. Water quality parameters (temperature, oxygen, ammonia, nitrate, and nitrite) were regularly monitored and kept within optimal ranges. After each feeding, feces were siphoned from the tanks. During acclimation, fish were fed commercial pellets *ad libitum* to adapt to the experimental feeding regime.

All animal procedures complied with the ethical guidelines of the Swedish Board of Agriculture (permit no. 15984–2018). The fish were monitored daily, and no signs of stress or abnormal behavior were observed throughout the experiment.

Two treatments were applied for the feeding trial: a negative control (no MPs) and an exposure group fed with an MP mixture (PP, PET, PE, and PA6; particle sizes 10–350 μm). Each treatment included 11 fish, housed in pairs in tanks and separated by dividers. The feeding trial lasted seven days, during which each fish was fed individually once per day until satiation (3–5 g food/day), corresponding to an estimated total MP intake of $(4.2\text{--}7.0) \times 10^5$ μg per fish. Feces were collected daily by gentle suction from the tank bottom, transferred into pre-cleaned glass vials, and frozen at -20 °C until analysis. Feces samples were subsequently sent to the National Institute of Chemistry (Ljubljana, Slovenia) for qualitative μ -FTIR analysis.

At the end of exposure, fish were euthanized by spinal cord severance, and their weight and fork length were recorded. No significant differences in these parameters were observed between the control and exposed groups. Fillet, liver, and gonad samples were collected under contamination-controlled conditions following (Sefiloglu et al., 2024). No visible plastic fibers or fragments were observed during dissection. The samples were wrapped in aluminum foil, placed on dry ice, and transported to Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (the Netherlands) for analysis by Py-GC-MS.

2.3. Sample treatment for MP extraction

2.3.1. Treatment of liver, gonad, and muscle tissues

The liver, gonad, and fillet samples were treated to extract the MPs from tissues and remove organic matter for the subsequent Py-GC-MS analysis. A total of 22 liver, 22 gonad, and 22 fillet samples (11 control and 11 MP-fed for each tissue type) went through the sample preparation protocol using the method developed by Sefiloglu et al. (2024).

All tissues were first freeze-dried (Christ Alpha 1–4, Germany) separately in precleaned glass vials. The dried tissues were then cut with

a surgical knife and homogenized in the same glass vials in the laminar flow cabinet. For fillet and liver samples, 250 mg of dried subsamples were taken, representing 23 % and 4 % of the initial sample dry weight, respectively. In the case of the gonads, the entire dried tissue was analyzed, as the remaining average weight after drying was only 0.27 mg.

The samples were chemically digested in the glass tubes with 20 mL of 10 % KOH (Honeywell, USA) and 6 mL of NaClO (6 %–14 % active chlorine, Supelco, USA). The suspension is first homogenized using an ultrasonic probe (Fischer Scientific, USA) and incubated overnight at 50 °C and 55 rpm in a water bath. The digested samples were then neutralized with acetic acid (99.8 %, Sigma Aldrich, USA) and diluted with isopropanol (99.95 %, Biosolve, France) to obtain a filterable solution. The samples were filtered through a 0.7 µm glass filter (GF/F, Whatman, United Kingdom) and collected on an 8 mm diameter section of the filter using a customized filtration system. After filtration, the filter was rinsed with 5 mL acetic acid: water (1:1, v/v) solution followed by 5 mL of ethanol, and then treated with 2 mL hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30 %, Supelco, USA) for 10 min. Final rinsing was done with 5 mL of water and 5 mL of ethanol. The 8 mm section of the filter containing the analyte residues was cut out, folded, and transferred to the pyrolysis cups. Samples were dried and kept in the nitrogen purge oven at 50 °C (Binder, Emurgo, Landsmeer, the Netherlands) before the Py-GC-MS analysis.

It should be noted that each tissue sample has a different lipid and protein content. During filtration, clogging of the homogenized solution was occasionally observed in liver samples. In such cases, 30 % H₂O₂ was added directly onto the filter to dissolve residual organic matter, which cleared the blockage and allowed complete filtration of the sample through the designated filter area.

2.3.2. Treatment of fecal matter

For the treatment and analysis of fecal samples, various digestion protocols were tested. These protocols involved H₂O₂ oxidation combined with density separation and additional reagents. The results identified the optimal protocol for maximizing organic matter removal and MP separation (detailed in Section 3.1.2).

In the final method, 2 g of dried fecal material were mixed with 147 mL of a reagent solution containing Fenton's reagent, H₂O₂ (30 %, Merck Sigma), and nitric acid (HNO₃, Honeywell Fluka) in a 2:4:1 (v/v/v) ratio. Fenton's reagent was prepared by dissolving 20 g of iron(II) sulfate (≥99.0 %, Sigma-Aldrich) in 1 L of ultrapure water. The mixture was incubated at 50 °C for 24 h. After the digestion, the samples were filtered under vacuum through a 10 µm stainless steel mesh.

2.4. MP analysis

2.4.1. Py-GC-MS analysis

MPS extracted from liver, gonad, and muscle tissues collected from 11 MP-exposed and 11 control fish were identified and quantified using Py-GC-MS. For each fish, one sample per tissue type was analyzed. A double-shot Py-GC-MS analysis was performed using a multi-shot pyrolyzer EGA/PY-3030D (Frontier Laboratories, Saikon, Japan), which is connected to an Agilent 6890 gas chromatograph coupled with a 5975C mass spectrometer (Santa Clara CA, USA). Agilent DB-5HT column (30m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm) was used with helium as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 3 mL/min. The analysis conditions were identical to the previous study by Sefiloglu et al. (2024). The details of the instrumental conditions and analysis are summarized in Table S2, and the summary of pyrolysis products used for the identification and quantification of polymers is shown in Table S3.

2.4.2. µ-FTIR and optical microscopy analysis

MPS extracted from the feces of four exposed and one control samples were qualitatively identified using µ-FTIR and optical microscopy. FTIR spectra of the MPS were recorded on a Bruker Lumos in attenuated total

reflection (ATR) mode using a diamond crystal in the frequency region of 600 cm⁻¹ - 4000 cm⁻¹. The FTIR signal was obtained by averaging 64 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Optical microscopy images of MPS were acquired using a LEICA DMS 1000 digital stereo microscope with a coded lens having a resolution of 5 megapixels and magnifications up to 300.

2.5. Quality assurance and control for Py-GC-MS analysis

To evaluate method performance for different tissues and polymer types, spiking experiments were conducted on liver, gonad, and fillet samples from another batch of regular tilapia originating from the same RAS facility. 250 mg of freeze-dried tissues were spiked with 4 µg of PE, PP, and PA standards in triplicate, and the sample treatment procedure was applied. PET was excluded from the target list, as previous experiments showed no recovery for this polymer (Sefiloglu et al., 2024). Details of the standards used for spiking experiments is shown in Table S4.

Spiked tissues (n = 3) were subjected to the full digestion and analysis procedure. Unspiked tissues (n = 3) underwent the same treatment in triplicate and subsequently had the same amount of polymers added directly to the pyrolysis cups; these were designated as control samples. Polymer recovery (%) for each matrix was calculated as the ratio of signal response in the spiked sample to that in the corresponding control sample, multiplied by 100.

The effect of different matrices on the responses of the indicator compounds was also evaluated. Reference samples (n = 3) were prepared by adding the same amount of polymers to pyrolysis cups containing a clean filter in triplicate. The matrix effect (%) was calculated based on the ratio of indicator compound responses in the control samples containing matrix versus reference samples without the matrix ((control sample/reference sample - 1) × 100).

Procedural blanks (n = 8) were included in each analytical batch and processed using identical digestion steps without tissue. Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) for each indicator compound were determined as three and ten times the standard deviation of the quantifier ion responses in the blanks, respectively. Polymer concentrations exceeding the LOD in tissue samples were corrected using the average procedural blank concentration. A summary of QA/QC parameters is provided in Table S5.

2.6. Contamination control

To prevent any external contamination with MPS, measures were implemented within the three laboratories involved in this study. In all laboratories, 100 % cotton lab coats were worn during sample preparation and analysis, and the usage of plastic materials was avoided. The workbenches were cleaned daily with 70 % ethanol, all glassware was rinsed with demineralized water, which was filtered through a 0.7 µm pre-muffled microfiber glass filter (Whatman Maidstone, United Kingdom). Samples were stored in plastic-free aluminum foil or pre-cleaned glass vials. For the sensitive analysis with Py-GC-MS, further precautions were taken within the laboratory. Glassware underwent heating in a muffle oven at 525 °C prior to use (CARBOLITE-Gero LHT6120-230SN). The samples were prepared in a laminar flow cabinet. Any items exposed to air, including samples, solvents, and tweezers, were promptly covered with aluminum foil. All glass filters used for filtration of the samples, solvents, and the demineralized cleaning water were subjected to heat treatment at 500 °C within a glass Petri dish. The stainless-steel pyrolysis cups (Eco-cup LF, Frontier Laboratories, Saikon, Japan), were also pre-heated in a flame until they reached a high temperature to remove possible contamination. With each batch of samples, a procedural blank sample was analyzed to assess potential background contamination (See section 2.5.).

2.7. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted to evaluate potential differences in MP occurrence between control and exposed groups. Because most concentration values were below the limit of detection (LOD) and the sample size was relatively small ($n = 11$ per group), the data were treated as binary variables (presence = 1, absence = 0). Fisher's Exact Test was applied separately for each polymer type and tissue (liver and gonad) to determine whether the frequency of MP detection differed between groups. All analyses were performed in R (version 4.2.3; R Core Team, 2025) using a significance level of 0.05.

3. Results

3.1. Sample treatment for MP extraction

3.1.1. Treatment of liver, gonad, and fillet tissues

Recoveries and matrix effects for PE, PP, and PA6 were determined across all three matrices including liver, gonad, and fillet (Fig. 1., Table S6). Polymer recoveries were assessed by comparing the responses of indicator compounds in spiked matrices to those in control samples containing the same polymers in an unspiked matrix extract.

The method demonstrated good recoveries for PE and PP in all three matrices, ranging from 81 ± 12 – 107 ± 7.8 % and 78 ± 9.5 – 88 ± 12 %, respectively (Table S6). Matrix effects were assessed by comparing the responses of the indicator compounds in control samples to those in reference standards containing clean filters spiked with the same amount of polymers. For PE and PP, the matrix effects on the responses of the selected indicator ions were within the range of ± 20 %. The recovery of PA6 was initially tested using procedural blanks without a matrix, yielding a recovery of 68 ± 7 %, which was considered acceptable. However, when a matrix was present, the recovery for PA6 was found within the range of 30 ± 24 – 53 ± 16 %, with average matrix effects ranging from -12 % to -39 % (Fig. 1.). Although a similar

digestion protocol and analysis method were applied, Zhong et al. (2022) reported recoveries of >80 % for PA6 from mussels. In that study, mussel samples were digested with 10 % KOH for 2 h. The differences in recoveries observed in this study may be attributed to the longer digestion duration, the inclusion of additional reactants such as H_2O_2 and acetic acid for complete digestion and improved filterability, and the increased complexity of the biological matrices analyzed. While PA6 was quantified in the samples, it is important to note that the reported concentrations may be underestimated due to the low recoveries.

3.1.2. Treatment of the fish feces

Previous studies have proposed several approaches for extracting MPs from fecal matter of different organisms (Beriot et al., 2021; Toto et al., 2023). However, a standardized protocol for fish feces remains unavailable. In the present study, different digestion protocols were tested to extract MPs from fecal matter with minimal interferences caused by organic matter. Fig. 2 shows the resulting extract of different digestion protocols.

Initial treatment of 2 g of fecal material with H_2O_2 at 50 °C for 48 h, followed by density separation using zinc chloride ($ZnCl_2$, density = 1.7 g/cm³), did not achieve complete digestion of organic matter. Organic residues remained suspended in the supernatant instead of settling, hindering MP isolation (Fig. 2a). Similar results were obtained by Yan et al. (2020) when separating MPs from fish feces using NaI (1.8 g/cm³). Subsequent oxidation using Fenton's reagent combined with H_2O_2 in a 1:2 (v/v) ratio and heating at 50 °C for 24 h improved organic matter removal but did not achieve complete digestion (Fig. 2b). Optimal results were obtained when fecal samples were treated with a mixture of 147 mL of Fenton's reagent, H_2O_2 , and HNO_3 in a 2:4:1 (v/v/v) ratio and incubated at 50 °C for 24 h. This treatment resulted in efficient removal of organic impurities and clear separation of MPs (Fig. 2c). The extracted MPs were subsequently filtered through a 10 μ m stainless-steel mesh and prepared for characterization.

To evaluate the effect of the reagent MPs, the MP mixture that was

Fig. 1. Recovery and average matrix effect of polymers (PA6: polyamide-6, PE: polyethylene, and PP: polypropylene) in different tissues (L: liver, G: gonad, F: fillet) following the applied sample treatment methods. Bars represent mean recoveries (%) with standard deviation as error bars, and small squares indicate the mean matrix effect (%).

Fig. 2. Comparison of fish feces treated with (a) H_2O_2 , (b) H_2O_2 combined with Fenton's reagent, and (c) H_2O_2 , Fenton's reagent, and HNO_3 2:4:1 (v/v/v), filtered through a 10 μm mesh metal filter.

used for the feeding experiments was treated with the optimized protocol (50 °C for 24 h), and polymers were then analyzed with $\mu\text{-FTIR}$. The results indicated no spectral changes for PE, PP, and PET (Fig. 3). However, PA6 was completely oxidized during the treatment and could not be recovered for analysis. FTIR spectral band assignments for PE, PP, PET, and PA6 are listed in Table S7.

3.2. MP analysis

3.2.1. MP concentrations in liver, gonad, and fillet samples

PE, PP, and PA6 were analyzed in the liver, gonad, and fillet samples from 11 control tilapia and 11 tilapia exposed to MPs using Py-GC-MS. The individual polymer concentrations in liver and gonad samples in control and fed samples were summarized in Fig. 4, and listed in Tables S8 and S9.

In the control group (CO01-CO11) fed with regular feed, PE was detected in the liver of four samples (CO3, CO6, CO10, CO11) averaging

Fig. 3. FTIR Spectra of polyethylene (PE; a), polypropylene (PP; b), polyethylene terephthalate (PET; c), polyamide 6 (PA6; d) before (purple) and after digestion (orange) using the optimized treatment method for fecal matter. As PA6 was completely oxidized, no post-digestion spectrum is available for this polymer.

Fig. 4. Mass concentrations (>LOD) of polymers detected in 22 tilapia samples. CO: control group fed with normal feed (n = 11, CO1-CO11); MP: group fed with microplastics (n = 11, MP1-MP11). Note the different scales between the two panels. PA6: polyamide-6; PE: polyethylene; PP: polypropylene.

$0.23 \pm 0.34 \mu\text{g/g}$ wet weight (ww), while no targeted polymers were found above the LOD in the gonad or fillet samples. The detection of PE in the liver of the control group may be attributed to the extensive use of PE in the aquaculture system (tanks, fittings etc.) where the tilapia was grown.

In the MP-exposed group fed with MP-containing feed (MP01-MP11), five liver samples contained MPs with an average concentration of $0.68 \pm 1.28 \mu\text{g/g}$ ww. PE and PP were detected in these five liver samples (MP4, MP7, MP8, MP10, MP11), while PA was identified in two (MP8, MP11). In the gonads of exposed tilapia, four samples (MP2, MP4, MP7, MP11) contained only PE residues, with concentrations averaging $0.29 \pm 0.59 \mu\text{g/g}$ ww. Interestingly, none of the targeted polymers were detected above the LOD in the fillet samples of MP-exposed tilapia.

The average total MP concentrations in exposed liver and gonad samples were found as $0.68 \pm 1.28 \mu\text{g/g}$ ww and $0.29 \pm 0.59 \mu\text{g/g}$ ww, respectively (Table S9). Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences between the control and exposed groups in PE concentrations in the gonad ($p = 0.090$) and liver ($p = 1.000$) samples. PP concentrations in the liver of the exposed group were significantly different than those in the control group ($p = 0.035$). No significant difference was observed in PA6 concentrations between the control and exposed groups in liver samples ($p = 0.476$).

Based on the feed consumption of 3–5 g per fish per day, the daily MP exposure was estimated to range between 6.0×10^4 to $1.0 \times 10^5 \mu\text{g}$, corresponding to a total ingestion of $(4.2\text{--}7.0) \times 10^5 \mu\text{g}$ over the 7-day exposure period. Despite this high level of MP exposure, the concentrations detected in the organs (liver and gonads) were significantly lower, and no evidence of translocation to the fillet tissues was observed. It is worth noting that the liver subsamples analyzed represented approximately one-quarter of the entire liver, whereas the whole gonad and 4 % of the fillet were analyzed. When extrapolated to the entire liver, the accumulation of MPs in the liver for the five tilapia with detectable residues was estimated to range from 0.36 to 7.56 μg . This corresponds to a maximum accumulation of approximately 0.001 % of the total ingested MPs. However, this value should be evaluated with caution, as more than half of the exposed fish showed no detectable MPs in any of the analyzed tissues. It should also be noted that the digestion protocols applied in this study may cause underestimation of some polymers, including PA6 and PET, due to the low recovery.

3.2.2. MP occurrence in fish feces

Four fecal samples from exposed fish were analyzed by $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ for

qualitative identification of MPs. All samples contained detectable MPs, with a total of 30 particles identified, comprising 14 PE, 6 PP, and 10 PET particles. PA6 was not detected, likely due to complete degradation during digestion, although its presence in the feed suggested potential exposure. Representative PE, PP, and PET particles recovered from the feces are shown in Fig. 5. The corresponding $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ spectra and images of all identified MPs are available in the Zenodo repository (see Data Availability section). To evaluate possible contamination, fecal samples from control fish were also examined, in which four blue fibers were observed (Supplementary Fig. S1).

4. Discussion

The low levels of MP residues observed in the liver, gonad, and fillet tissues, combined with the high abundance of MPs in the fecal matter, suggest that particles in the size range of 10–350 μm are predominantly excreted from the body after ingestion. This can be attributed to the relatively large particle size, which exceeds the typical threshold (<10 μm) for absorption across intestinal epithelia. Larger irregular particles are likely retained within the gastrointestinal lumen and subsequently eliminated through fecal excretion. The short exposure duration and effective gut clearance mechanisms of tilapia further reduce the potential for tissue retention (Ghosh, 2025).

Previous studies on marine organisms have reported high excretion rates (>90 %) of MPs following ingestion (Pérez-Guevara et al., 2021). These studies primarily focus on analyzing the digestive tract of organisms post-exposure to understand excretion rates (Hou et al., 2023; Yong et al., 2021). However, quantitative analysis of MPs in fecal matter remains an important knowledge gap. Such research could provide valuable insights into the egestion dynamics of MPs and improve models of their environmental fate, particularly as fecal matter itself may act as a vector for MP pollution (Pérez-Guevara et al., 2021).

Similar to the results obtained in this study, low bioaccumulation of particles in targeted organs and fillet samples has been observed in other exposure studies conducted under controlled conditions (Dawson et al., 2025; Kim et al., 2020; Zeytin et al., 2020). Studies vary in terms of the polymer types, sizes, shapes, and concentrations of the particles used, as well as the duration of exposure, the species studied, the analyzed organs or tissues, and the analytical methods applied. However, a common finding is that the GIT serves as the main site of accumulation, while accumulation in the liver and gonads, as well as translocation to fillet tissues, remains comparatively very low.

Fig. 5. Optical microscopy images of (a) polyethylene (PE), (b) polypropylene (PP), and (c) polyethylene terephthalate (PET) particles extracted from the feces of microplastic-exposed fish. Scale bar = 200 μm .

In the study of Dawson et al. (2025), Juvenile barramundi (*Lates calcifer*) was exposed to PA and PET fibers with 8–547 μm length via feed. Analysis of the GIT, liver, and muscle tissues showed no accumulation of MPs in the liver or muscle within two days post-exposure, while more than 90 % of the ingested particles were egested within 24 h. In the study of Kim et al. (2020) adult rainbow trout were fed fluorescent PE microspheres mixed into regular feed, and their liver, gonad, and fillet tissues were analyzed after 14 days of dietary exposure. Similar to the present study, the particles used were within the 10–300 μm size range, and no evidence of PE microsphere translocation to the analyzed tissues was found using fluorescent microscopy. Instead, the particles were predominantly located in the gut after 24 h of feeding, suggesting that they were mostly excreted. In another study, Zeytin et al. (2020) quantified MP accumulation in the fillet tissues of juvenile European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) after 16 weeks of dietary exposure to fluorescent PS particles (1–5 μm). Based on fluorescent microscopy analysis, a translocation rate of 1 MP particle reaching the fillet for every 1.87×10^7 particles ingested was estimated. Despite the smaller size of the PS beads used for exposure (<10 μm), the translocation rate to the fillet was found to be extremely low.

While the dietary exposure studies on Nile tilapia are limited, several studies have investigated the uptake and translocation of waterborne MPs. Das et al. (2023) investigated the accumulation of fluorescent PS microbeads (1 μm) in Nile tilapia. The fish were exposed to three concentrations (0.01, 0.1 and 1 mg/L) in tank water for 14 days. MP accumulation was observed in all organs, including the gut, gills, spleen, liver, gonad, muscle, and brain. Similarly, Muhib and Rahman (2024) exposed Nile tilapia to a mixture of plastics sourced from a local plastic processing factory, ground to a size range of 13–5000 μm , for 60 days. Visual inspection under a stereomicroscope showed that the GIT accumulated the highest levels of MPs, whereas gills and muscle tissues retained comparatively fewer particles.

Observations from controlled exposure studies align with findings from field analyses, where the GIT consistently emerges as the most susceptible site for MP accumulation (Matias et al., 2023; Pitt et al., 2024). As some field studies reported no translocation to fillet samples (Pedram Jarf et al., 2024), other studies have reported the presence of MPs in the liver (Piskuła et al., 2025) and fillet tissues (Blonç et al., 2023; Haave et al., 2024) of different species and different environments. This highlights the numerous factors influencing MP exposure in natural environments, such as unknown exposure concentrations and durations, potential biomagnification, epithelial barrier function of the GIT or other tissues, the life span of the organisms, and variations in ecological and biological conditions (Ghosh, 2025; Koraltan et al., 2022).

From a food safety perspective, the findings of the present study, along with the comparative literature, suggest that the risk of direct human exposure to MPs via consumption of tilapia fillet may be relatively low compared to other dietary sources (WHO, 2022). However, even low concentration burdens warrant caution, given the emerging evidence of MPs influencing oxidative stress and tissue damage in fish (Bhuyan, 2022) or acting as carriers for adsorbed contaminants (e.g.,

heavy metals, pesticides, persistent organic pollutants) (Kinigopoulou et al., 2022). For aquaculture management, the detection of PE particles in the liver of control fish in the present study, together with the trace amounts of MPs previously reported in fish fillets from RAS systems (Sefiloglu et al., 2024), underscores the importance of minimizing MP exposure in farmed fish by closely monitoring and improving the quality of both feed and rearing water.

5. Conclusions

In the present study, the translocation and accumulation of MPs in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) were evaluated following dietary exposure under controlled conditions for a period of seven days. Fish were exposed to a mixture of four polymer types (PE, PP, PET, PA6) with irregular shapes, and liver, gonad, and fillet tissues were analyzed using Py-GC-MS, while fecal samples were examined qualitatively via μ -FTIR and optical microscopy. The observation of minimal MP accumulation in liver and gonad tissues, and no MPs in fillet samples, indicates limited translocation and bioaccumulation of particles within the tested size range (10–350 μm). The high MP content detected in fecal matter demonstrated efficient excretion as the dominant elimination pathway. These results suggest that short-term dietary exposure to MPs in the targeted size range does not lead to accumulation in edible tissues of tilapia and that the risk of human exposure through fish consumption under such conditions is low. The findings contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of MP translocation in aquaculture species through dietary exposure and highlight the need for further studies addressing longer exposure durations, different polymer characteristics, and the potential role of associated chemical additives.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Feride Öykü Sefiloglu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Vaibhav Budhiraja:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Azora König Kardgar:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Marthinus Brits:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Martin J.M. van Velzen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Andrej Kržan:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Darragh Doyle:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Bethanie Carney Almroth:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Marja H. Lamoree:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT 4 in

order to improve the language and readability. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 860720 and HORIZON research and innovation actions under grant agreement No 101134958.

The authors acknowledge discussions with Jacco Koekoek and thank Quinn Groenewoud for their support in the laboratory.

We are grateful for the inspiration that collaboration with Dick Vethaak, who sadly passed away on June 1, 2024, has given us.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2025.108164>.

Data availability

The raw data from Py-GC-MS and μ -FTIR analysis, and images of detected particles in fecal matter are available in the Zenodo repository, 10.5281/zenodo.15031996.

References

- Beriot, N., Peek, J., Zornoza, R., Geissen, V., & Huerta Lwanga, E. (2021). Low density-microplastics detected in sheep faeces and soil: A case study from the intensive vegetable farming in Southeast Spain. *Science of the Total Environment*, 755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142653>
- Bhuyan, M. S. (2022). Effects of microplastics on fish and in human health. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.827289>. Frontiers Media S.A.
- Blonc, M., Husson, F., Llorca, M., Farré, M., Tort, L., Brandts, I., & Teles, M. (2023). Occurrence of micro-nanoplastics in a commercial recirculated aquaculture system and their translocation to cultured fish organs: A baseline study. *Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hazadv.2023.100381>
- Das, B. C., Ramanan, P. A., Gorakh, S. S., Pillai, D., & Vattiringal Jayadradhan, R. K. (2023). Sub-chronic exposure of *Oreochromis niloticus* to environmentally relevant concentrations of smaller microplastics: Accumulation and toxico-physiological responses. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.131916>
- Dawson, A. L., Santana, M. F. M., Perez, M., Meehan, K., McCarthy, H., Vickers, K., & Motti, C. A. (2025). Rapid egestion of microplastics in juvenile barramundi: No evidence of gut retention or tissue translocation. *Environmental Pollution*, 370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2025.125884>
- Egea-Corbacho, A., Martín-García, A. P., Franco, A. A., Albendín, G., Arellano, J. M., Rodríguez-Barroso, R., Coello, M. D., Quiroga, J. M., Cabello, J. F., Iglesias Prado, I., & Malta, E. Jan (2023). Microplastic in industrial aquaculture: Occurrence in the aquatic environment, feed and organisms (*Dicentrarchus labrax*). *Science of the Total Environment*, 904. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.166774>
- FAO. (2022). The state of world fisheries and aquaculture 2022 towards blue transformation. In *The state of world fisheries and aquaculture 2022*. FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc0461en>.
- Ferrante, M., Pietro, Z., Allegui, C., Maria, F., Antonio, C., Pulvirenti, E., Favara, C., Chiara, C., Grasso, A., Omayma, M., Gea, O. C., & Banni, M. (2022). Microplastics in fillets of mediterranean seafood. A risk assessment study. *Environmental Research*, 204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.112247>
- Gayathri, V., Pavithra, R., Thangal, S. H., Ganapathy, S., Gurusaravanan, P., Santhanam, P., Radhakrishnan, S., & Muralisankar, T. (2024). Incidence of microplastics in Indian anchovy *Stolephorus indicus* from Tuticorin, Southeast coast of India. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.116406>
- Ghosh, T. (2025). Microplastics bioaccumulation in fish: Its potential toxic effects on hematology, immune response, neurotoxicity, oxidative stress, growth, and reproductive dysfunction. *Toxicology Reports*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2024.101854>. Elsevier Inc.
- Haave, M., Hæggernes, E., & Gomiero, A. (2024). Absence of microplastic bioaccumulation in cod filets from plastic-polluted western Norwegian waters. *Water Emerging Contaminants and Nanoplastics*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.20517/wecn.2024.07>
- Hou, L., McNeish, R., & Hoellein, T. J. (2023). Egestion rates of microplastic fibres in fish scaled to in situ concentration and fish density. *Freshwater Biology*, 68(1), 33–45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fwb.14007>
- Kim, J., Poirier, D. G., Helm, P. A., Bayoumi, M., & Rochman, C. M. (2020). No evidence of spherical microplastics (10–300 μ m) translocation in adult rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) after a two-week dietary exposure. *PLoS One*, 15(9 September 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239128>
- Kinigiopoulou, V., Pashalidis, I., Kalderis, D., & Anastopoulos, I. (2022). Microplastics as carriers of inorganic and organic contaminants in the environment: A review of recent progress. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2022.118580>. Elsevier B.V.
- König Kardgar, A., Doyle, D., Warwas, N., Hjelset, T., Sundh, H., & Carney Almroth, B. (2024). Microplastics in aquaculture - Potential impacts on inflammatory processes in Nile tilapia. *Heliyon*, 10(9), Article e30403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e30403>
- Koralan, İ., Mavruk, S., & Güven, O. (2022). Effect of biological and environmental factors on microplastic ingestion of commercial fish species. *Chemosphere*, 303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.135101>
- Li, B., Liang, W., Liu, Q. X., Fu, S., Ma, C., Chen, Q., Su, L., Craig, N. J., & Shi, H. (2021). Fish ingest microplastics unintentionally. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 55(15), 10471–10479. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c01753>
- Martins, C. I. M., Eding, E. H., Verdegem, M. C. J., Heinsbroek, L. T. N., Schneider, O., Blancheton, J. P., d'Orbecastel, E. R., & Verreth, J. A. J. (2010). New developments in recirculating aquaculture systems in Europe: A perspective on environmental sustainability. *Aquacultural Engineering*, 43(3), 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2010.09.002>
- Matias, R. S., Gomes, S., Barboza, L. G. A., Salazar-Gutierrez, D., Guilhermino, L., & Valente, L. M. P. (2023). Microplastics in water, feed and tissues of European seabass reared in a recirculation aquaculture system (RAS). *Chemosphere*, 335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.139055>
- Muhib, M. I., & Rahman, M. M. (2024). How do fish consume microplastics? An experimental study on accumulation pattern using Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 31(27), 39303–39317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-33782-0>
- Ouheddu, M., Abelouah, M. R., Ben-Haddad, M., Hajji, S., Laaraj, N. eddine, Akhouchal, I., Barra, I., Rangel-Buitrago, N., Agnaou, M., & Alla, A. A. (2025). Microplastics in Morocco's most consumed fisheries: Chemical characterization, ecological traits, and implications for human health. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.117334>
- Pedram Jarf, M., Kamali, A., Khara, H., Pourang, N., & Shekarabi, S. P. H. (2024). Microplastic pollution and heavy metal risk assessment in Perca fluviatilis from Anzali wetland: Implications for environmental health and human consumption. *Science of the Total Environment*, 907. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167978>
- Pereira, R., Rodrigues, S. M., Silva, D., Freitas, V., Almeida, C. M. R., & Ramos, S. (2023). Microplastic contamination in large migratory fishes collected in the open Atlantic Ocean. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114454>
- Pérez-Guevara, F., Roy, P. D., Kutralam-Muniasamy, G., & Shruti, V. C. (2021). A central role for fecal matter in the transport of microplastics: An updated analysis of new findings and persisting questions. *Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hazadv.2021.100021>
- Piskula, P., Astel, A., & Pawlik, M. (2025). Microplastics in seawater and fish acquired from the corresponding fishing zones of the Baltic sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.117485>
- Pitt, J. A., Gallager, S. M., Youngs, S., Michel, A. P. M., Hahn, M. E., & Aluru, N. (2024). The abundance and localization of environmental microplastics in gastrointestinal tract and muscle of Atlantic killifish (*Fundulus heteroclitus*): A pilot study. *Microplastics and Nanoplastics*, 4(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43591-024-00101-w>
- Piyawardhana, N., Weerathunga, V., Chen, H. S., Guo, L., Huang, P. J., Ranatunga, R. R. M. K. P., & Hung, C. C. (2022). Occurrence of microplastics in commercial marine dried fish in Asian countries. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.127093>
- Rojas-Luna, R. A., Rueda-Reyes, P. A., García-Alzate, C. A., García-Alzate, R., Trilleras, J., Medina-Calderon, J. H., Santos-Martínez, A., Pineda, J. E. M., Sierra, C. A., & Arana, V. A. (2025). Widespread microplastic ingestion in Colombian Caribbean marine fish: Trophic influence, spatial-temporal trends, and polymer composition. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2025.118603>
- Sefilloglu, F.Ö., Brits, M., König Kardgar, A., van Velzen, M. J. M., Kaldenbach, E., Vethaak, A. D., Doyle, D., Carney Almroth, B., & Lamoree, M. H. (2024). Quantitative analysis of microplastics in Nile tilapia from a recirculating aquaculture system using pyrolysis-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 36(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-024-00987-6>
- Sun, X., Meng, L., Liang, J., Li, Q., Du, J., Zhu, M., Zhao, Y., & Zheng, S. (2025). Microplastic distribution patterns in fish and implications for safe consumption. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 59(33), 17393–17402. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5c02907>
- Toto, B., Refosco, A., Dierkes, J., & Kögel, T. (2023). Efficient extraction of small microplastic particles from rat feed and feces for quantification. *Heliyon*, 9(1), Article e12811. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e12811>

- Wang, Z., Chen, S., He, Y., Liang, L., & Jiang, Z. (2024). Fish guts possess higher priority in assessing ecological risk of microplastics in both fish bodies and aquatic environments. *Ecological Indicators*, 168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.112792>
- WHO. (2022). *Dietary and inhalation exposure to nano-and microplastic particles and potential implications for human health*.
- Yan, Z., Zhao, H., Zhao, Y., Zhu, Q., Qiao, R., Ren, H., & Zhang, Y. (2020). An efficient method for extracting microplastics from feces of different species. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.121489>
- Yong, M. M. H., Leistenschneider, C., Miranda, J. A., Paler, M. K., Legaspi, C., Germanov, E., Araujo, G., Burkhardt-Holm, P., & Erni-Cassola, G. (2021). Microplastics in fecal samples of whale sharks (*Rhincodon typus*) and from surface water in the Philippines. *Microplastics and Nanoplastics*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43591-021-00017-9>
- Zeytin, S., Wagner, G., Mackay-Roberts, N., Gerdtts, G., Schuirmann, E., Klockmann, S., & Slater, M. (2020). Quantifying microplastic translocation from feed to the fillet in European sea bass *Dicentrarchus labrax*. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111210>
- Zhong, Y., Bao, Q., Yuan, L., Liu, J., Cai, Y., & Chen, X. (2022). Analysis of microplastics in aquatic shellfish by pyrolysis-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry after alkali digestion and solvent extraction. *Polymers*, 14(18). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14183888>
- Zhou, A., Zhang, Y., Xie, S., Chen, Y., Li, X., Wang, J., & Zou, J. (2021). Microplastics and their potential effects on the aquaculture systems: A critical review. *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 13(1), 719–733. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12496>. Wiley-Blackwell.